

Difurfuryl Thiocarbohydrazone as a Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium(VI) and Iridium(III)

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Thiocarbohydrazone have been suggested as selective reagent for the photometric determination of platinum metals¹. These stable compounds having the general formula RCH=NNHCSNHN=CHR behave as pentadentate dibasic ligand like dithizone with four coordinating nitrogen atoms and one thiol group. Difurfuryl thiocarbohydrazone (DFTCH) is examined now as a very sensitive and selective reagent for osmium(VI) and iridium(III).

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of Os and Ir complexes show $\lambda_{\max}$ at 377 and 380 nm respectively, where the reagent has comparatively low absorption.

The optimum pH range for the Os complex is 5.9–6.7 and that for the Ir complex 5.5–6.2. The Os complex is coloured brown and the Ir complex is yellow. Both the complexes are stable for more than 24 h. The empirical formula of the complexes were determined by the mole-ratio² and slope-ratio³ methods. The composition of the Os^{VI} and Ir^{III} complexes (reagent : metal) were found to be 2 : 1 and 3 : 1 respectively. The results of single extraction of the Os and Ir complexes using equal volumes of the solvent and water at 32° are shown in Table 1.

In case of the Os complex, 1,2-dichloroethane (DCE) show similar behaviour as that of ethyl acetate, but the complex formed in DCE is stable only for 6 h, after which

absorption decreases and $\lambda_{\max}$ drifts towards the shorter wavelength. Ethyl acetate was, therefore, used for extraction. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 1.0–4.2 (Os^{VI} complex) and 0.93–3.73 ppm (Ir^{III} complex). Spectral characteristics of the complexes are shown in Table 2. For Os complex with 59.85 μg of the metal, the average of determination was 59.57 which varied between 59.57 ± 0.2592 at 95% confidence limit. For iridium complex with 51.56 μg of the metal, the average of determination was found to be 51.09 μg which varied between 51.09 ± 0.4412 .

The tolerance limits for interference set at the amount required to cause an error not exceeding 3% in the determination of Os (59.85 μg) and Ir (51.56 μg) are as follows: V^V, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Au^{III}, U^{VI}, Bi^{III} (1000 μg) and Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II} (2000 μg). Further, tolerance limits (in μg) for estimation of Os are: Mo^{VI} (1000), Zn^{II} (2500), W^{VI} (1800), Rh (50), Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} (180), Ir^{III} (300) and Cu^{II} (500). The tolerance limits (in μg) for estimation of Ir are: W^{VI} and Zn^{II} (2000), Cu^{II} (1000), Mo^{VI} (800), Os^{VI} (250), Pd^{II} (240), Ru^{III} (370) and Pt^{IV} (360). Cr, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Pb were masked with EDTA, Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} were reduced to their bivalent state using NH₂OH.HCl and SO₂ respectively, before the estimation Pd and Os were extracted first in the cold condition for the estimation of iridium. Au³⁺ was reduced to Au with the reagent and its interference was avoided by filtering it off before the extraction. Hg interfered seriously. Interference of Pd could not be avoided for the estimation of osmium. Due to nonavailability of real samples, Os and Ir were studied by preparing synthetic mixtures. The results are given in Table 3.

Experimental

Stock solution of Ir was prepared by dissolving iridium chloride (Johnson and Mathey) in dilute HCl and standardised by hydrolytic precipitation method. Osmium solution was prepared by dissolving OsO₄ (Johnson and

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION RATIO (D) AND PERCENTAGE EXTRACTION (E) OF OS AND IR COMPLEXES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Solvent	Osmium		Iridium	
	D	% E	D	% E
Isobutyl methyl ketone	10.7	91.5	5.63	84.9
1,2-Dichloroethane	123.7	99.2	4.31	81.2
Chloroform	14.6	93.6	1.89	65.5
Benzene	1.5	60.6	3.38	77.2
Carbon tetrachloride	0.13	11.4	0.19	1.8
Ethyl acetate	123.7	99.2	53.85	98.2

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF IR AND OS COMPLEXES

Compd.	Molar absorptivity $10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	Optimum concentration range ppm	Sandell's* sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$	Relative** Mean error %	Standard** deviation	Coeff.** of variation %
Os-DFTCH	3.62	1.0–4.2	0.0053	0.3217	0.2470	0.4146
Ir-DFTCH	4.15	0.93–3.73	0.0047	0.6132	0.4203	0.8228

*Ref. 4. **From six identical sets of experiments.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF Os AND Ir IN BINARY AND SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Mixtures in µg	Metal ion found (µg)*	Relative mean error %
Os ^{VI} (59.82), Ru ^{III} (180), Ir ^{III} (333), Rh ^{III} (47), Pt ^{IV} (180)	Os ^{VI} 59.18 ± 0.25	0.20
Ir ^{II} (103.12), Ru ^{III} (180), Pd ^{II} (48), Os ^{VI} (120), Pt ^{IV} (180)	Ir ^{II} 102.87 ± 0.30	0.19
Binary mixtures in µg	Amount found (µg)	
	Os ^{VI}	Ir ^{III}
Os ^{VI} (29.92), Ir ^{III} (257.80)	29.68	258.1
Os ^{VI} (179.55), Ir ^{III} (51.56)	179.25	51.23
Os ^{VI} (59.85), Ir ^{III} (51.56)	59.37	51.32

*For five sets of experiments with 95% confidence limit.

Mathey) in 0.2 M NaOH and its Os content determined⁵. The stock solution of Os and Ir were diluted with distilled water. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared in distilled water or dilute HCl. Dilute HCl and 10% sodium acetate solution were used to maintain the acidity of the solutions. A $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ DFTCH solution was prepared in ethanol. All chemicals were of A.R. grade.

A Hitachi U-3210 spectrophotometer with 10 mm quartz cells was used. The pH was measured with a Systronic 331 pH meter.

Procedure : An aliquot containing known amount of Os^{VI} solution (reducing OsO₄ with alcohol) was diluted to

20 ml with distilled water and its pH adjusted to 5.9–6.7 with sodium acetate solution. The reagent solution (1–2 ml) was then added and allowed to stand for 15 min. The solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 ml). The extract was made up to 25 ml, dried and its absorbance measured at 377 nm against reagent blank.

An aliquot containing known amount of iridium was diluted to 20 ml with distilled water and its pH adjusted to 5.5–6.2. Then reagent solution (1–2 ml) was added and heated in a warm water-bath for 10–15 min. It was then cooled to room temperature, extracted with ethyl acetate, dried and its absorbance was measured at 380 nm against reagent blank.

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